

Differentiation of Irrationality of Economics Teachers

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Abstract

In carrying out their profession, economics teachers cannot escape from economic attitudes and behavior, which are present in their lives every day. Even though they have adequate mastery of economic knowledge, according to the field of study they teach, economics teachers are still often trapped in irrational attitudes and behavior, which are not in accordance with the basic principles of economics. This research aims to explain the irrational attitudes and behavior of Economics Teachers, differentiated based on the level of (1) professional capability, (2) appreciation of educational conditions, (3) subjective well-being, (4) appreciation of economic conditions and (5) commitment to emulate. The explanatory study was carried out using a deductive approach through quantitative methods. The research subjects were 264 secondary education economics teachers spread across the East Java region. Data collection was carried out using questionnaires and tests and the data collected was analyzed using variance analysis. The analysis process was carried out with the help of the statistical application program SPSS for iOS ver. 26. The research results prove that there are significant differences in the irrational behavior of economics teachers based on the level of professional capability, appreciation of educational conditions, subjective well-being, appreciation of economic conditions and commitment to emulate. From the results of this research, it was found that the higher the level of the differentiating variable, the higher the intensity of economics teachers' irrational behavior. By knowing the mapping of teachers' economic irrationality and its differential factors, teacher development programs can be formulated more contextually. As is known, the substance and learning materials for economic education at the secondary education level in Indonesia today are theoretical and less contextual.

Keywords: *Differentiation, Irrationality, Economics.*

Suggested citation: Wahyono, H. (2024). Differentiation of Irrationality of Economics Teachers. *European Journal of Contemporary Education and E-Learning*, 2(1), 257-267. DOI: 10.59324/ejceel.2024.2(1).22

Introduction

The development of formal economic education in Indonesia has, over time, been less anticipatory and adapted to the extraordinary dynamic development of economic science. The curriculum has changed since the 1975 curriculum to the current independent learning curriculum, the substance and study materials of economic education, especially in secondary schools, have not shifted to follow the very dynamic

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development of economic theory, in line with the very rapid development of the economic life of society, following the revolution. science and technology.

In public life since the beginning of the 21st Century, there has been widespread discussion and debate about the millennial economy, digital economy, neuroeconomics (euroeconomics) and behavioral economics (behavioral economics) which are no longer in accordance with orthodox economic theories. However, economic education curriculum developers, as well as professional associations of economic educators, have not been moved to revitalize the substance and study materials of economic education. This condition is exacerbated by our education system which is centralized in implementing the curriculum, which limits teachers from improvising in implementing their learning in schools.

As is known since the last decade of this century, behavioral economics has developed which no longer believes in the truth of orthodox economic assumptions, which state that humans as homo economicus, always care about themselves, to maximize their satisfaction and profits, so that humans are considered rational economic actors. Empirically, humans do not always behave as rational homo economicus. Humans in real life often act as homo sapiens and more often act irrationally (Thaler, 2017). The assumption held by conventional economists that economic humans always act rationally and prioritize personal interests to maximize their satisfaction and profits has been widely abandoned, in line with the development of behavioral economic studies and theories (Ogaki & Tanaka, 2017; Cartwright, 2018).

People in general are more afraid of facing potential losses, compared to the profits that can be obtained, so they tend to be reluctant to take risks. This is called loss aversion; Likewise, people tend to over-value the items they have bought or own, so they are reluctant to sell or dispose of them, even though the item actually has little or no longer economic value. Such a tendency is called the endowment effect; People in general also tend to get stuck in favorite choices, which are subjectively determined, and are reluctant to shift or change their choices. This is called confirmation bias; Likewise, in general, people also tend to participate in economic decision making. That's called herd behavior; Next, people in general also tend to conclude economic conditions and problems based on invalid and general data. This last thing is called survivor bias (Barberis, 2018).

The study of material in economic education is closely related to everyday life, because in general humanity is never separated from day to day economic problems. For this reason, economic education demands a contextual learning process, close to life phenomena. In developing learning, economics teachers are often required to relate their experiences in economic life with the topics taught in class, both in explaining concepts and providing illustrations. In this regard, problems often arise, because there is a mismatch between what is explained and illustrated in classroom learning, and the experience of economics teachers in decision making and economic actions or behavior in their daily lives.

It is interesting to examine the problem of irrational behavior as revealed above among economics teachers, who incidentally in carrying out their profession are involved in economic studies. An economics teacher should be able to appear as a figure who is wise in economics and managing his economic life, as well as being more prosperous, so that he is able to provide correct insight into economic life and be a role model for the students he teaches. In reality, this is not the case, it has been proven that many teachers in other fields of study are wiser in economics and live more prosperously,

because they are more rational and skilled in economics. For this reason, an explanatory study is needed regarding the irrationality of economic behavior of teachers in economics subjects and the differentiation based on it level of professional capability, appreciation of educational conditions, level of subjective well-being, appreciation of economic conditions and commitment to emulate students. Such a study is important to obtain empirical findings that can be used as material for developing programs to improve the quality of teachers in accordance with aspects of their economic life, so that they are better able to develop contextual learning.

Materials and Methods

In accordance with its objectives, this research was designed with a deductive approach and the type of research is explanatory, namely explaining the target variables studied, the irrational behavior of economics teachers, differentiated based on the level of professional capability, appreciation of educational conditions, level of subjective well-being, appreciation of economic conditions and commitment to emulate. The research population was all economics teachers who taught at state high schools in East Java. Based on data from the East Java Provincial Education Service, the population in question is 4,126 people and is spread across 38 cities/districts. To determine the research sample, purposively based on the eastern, western, northern, southern and central regions of the province, 6 cities/districts were selected as sampling areas, namely Tulungagung Regency, Jember Regency, Magetan Regency, Lamongan Regency, Malang City and Surabaya City. Furthermore, from a total population of 4,126 economics teachers, the sample size was determined based on the sampling formula for estimation of proportions without repetition (sampling without replacement) with an error rate of 5% and obtained a sample size of 263.74 (rounded to 264) economics teachers.

Sampling was carried out using proportional random sampling based on the number of teachers in each region selected as regional samples. The distribution of sample numbers by region can be tabulated as follows:

Table 1. Distribution of Research Samples

No	County town	Number of Samples
1.	Tulungagung	42
2.	Jember	52
3.	Magetan	44
4.	Lamongan	38
5.	Malang city	32
6.	City of Surabaya	56
Amount		264

There is one dependent variable and five independent variables in this research. The translation of each variable into indicators for the purposes of creating an instrument in the form of a questionnaire can be presented in the following table:

Table 2. Variable Description

No	Variable	Indicator
1.	The Irrationality of Economic Behavior	a. Loss Aversion
		b. endowment effect
		c. confirmation bias
		d. herd behavior
		e. survivor bias
2.	Professional capabilities	a. Professional duties
		b. Hots achievements in learning
		c. Mastery of learning material
		d. Quality of learning design
		e. Implementation of learning
		f. Learning assessment activities
		g. Self-development
3.	Appreciation of educational conditions	a. Assessment of educational conditions
		b. Critical attitude towards education policy
		c. A critical assessment of the educational environment in the workplace
		d. A critical assessment of the economics education curriculum
		e. Obsession with ideal economic education
4.	Subjective well-being	a. Self-esteem positivity
		b. Self-control ability
		c. Extraversion
		d. Optimistic attitude
		e. Social relations
		f. Inner peace
5.	Appreciation of economic conditions	a. Positive attitude towards macroeconomic conditions
		b. Critical attitude towards economic inequality
		c. Assessment of the success of economic development
		d. Critical assessment of economic policy
		e. Critical assessment of corruption
6.	Commitment to emulate	a. Economic behavior at school
		b. Appearance when teaching in class
		c. Illustration of economic experiences while teaching in class
		d. Discipline in teaching
		e. Professional behavior

The data collection technique in this research is a questionnaire with a total of 107 questionnaire items. Data collection was carried out in two ways, first by distributing it face-to-face at meetings at the Economics Subject Teachers' Conference (MGMP) (Surabaya City and Malang City) and secondly by distributing it online using a Google form which can be accessed via email or cellphone. Data analysis was carried out using variance analysis and the analysis process was carried out with the help of the statistical application program SPSS for iOS ver. 26.

Results

From the results of data collection, the irrational behavior of economics teachers can be described, as shown in the following table:

Table 3. Statistical Description of Irrational Behavior of Economics Teachers (Y)

	Element	Statistics
N	Valid	264
	Missing	0
Mean		85.125
Std. Error of Mean		.6265
Median		86,000
Mode		86.0
Std. Deviation		10.1799
Variance		103.631
Minimum		53.0
Maximum		118.0
Sum		22473.0

The distribution and normality of economics teachers' irrational behavior data can be more clearly depicted in the following histogram:

Figure 1. Histogram and Normality of Irrationality Behavior of Economics Teachers

Hypothesis Testing Results

1. There are differences in the irrational behavior of Economics Teachers based on professional capabilities.

The results of the first hypothesis test in this research can be presented in the following analysis results table:

Table 4. ANOVA

Irrational Behavior					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	6865.652	2	3432.826	43,943	,000
Within Groups	20389.223	261	78,120		
Total	27254.875	263			

	(I) Professional Capabilities	(J) Professional Capabilities	Mean Difference (IJ)	Std. Error	Sig.
Tuk ey HS D	Tall	Currently	4.7113*	1.2614	,001
		Low	12.9724*	1.3846	,000
	Currently	Tall	-4.7113*	1.2614	,001
		Low	8.2611*	1.4163	,000
	Low	Tall	-12.9724*	1.3846	,000
		Currently	-8.2611*	1.4163	,000
Sch effe	Tall	Currently	4.7113*	1.2614	,001
		Low	12.9724*	1.3846	,000
	Currently	Tall	-4.7113*	1.2614	,001
		Low	8.2611*	1.4163	,000
	Low	Tall	-12.9724*	1.3846	,000
		Currently	-8.2611*	1.4163	,000

2. There are differences in the irrational behavior of Economics Teachers based on appreciation of educational conditions.

The results of the first hypothesis test in this research can be presented in the following analysis results table:

Table 5. ANOVA

Irrational Behavior						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups		6792.458	2	3396.229	43,319	,000
Within Groups		20462.417	261	78,400		
Total		27254.875	263			
	(I) Appreciation of Education	(J) Appreciation of Education	Mean Difference (IJ)	Std. Error	Sig.	
Tuk ey HS D	Tall	Currently	7.3161*	1.4669	,000	
		Low	13.8008*	1.5006	,000	
	Currently	Tall	-7.3161*	1.4669	,000	
		Low	6.4847*	1.2247	,000	
	Low	Tall	-13.8008*	1.5006	,000	
		Currently	-6.4847*	1.2247	,000	
Sch effe	Tall	Currently	7.3161*	1.4669	,000	
		Low	13.8008*	1.5006	,000	
	Currently	Tall	-7.3161*	1.4669	,000	
		Low	6.4847*	1.2247	,000	
	Low	Tall	-13.8008*	1.5006	,000	
		Currently	-6.4847*	1.2247	,000	

3. There are differences in the irrational behavior of Economics Teachers based on the level of subjective well-being.

The results of the first hypothesis test in this research can be presented in the following analysis results table:

Table 6. ANOVA

Irrational Behavior						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups		6969.343	2	3484.671	44,835	,000
Within Groups		20285.532	261	77,722		
Total		27254.875	263			
	(i) Subjective Well-being	(j) Subjective Well-Being	Mean Difference (Ij)		Std. Error	Sig.
Tuk ey HS D	Tall	Currently	8.1813*		1.6104	,000
		Low	14.2536*		1.5438	,000
	Currently	Tall	-8.1813*		1.6104	,000
		Low	6.0723*		1.2015	,000
	Low	Tall	-14.2536*		1.5438	,000
		Currently	-6.0723*		1.2015	,000
Sch effe	Tall	Currently	8.1813*		1.6104	,000
		Low	14.2536*		1.5438	,000
	Currently	Tall	-8.1813*		1.6104	,000
		Low	6.0723*		1.2015	,000
	Low	Tall	-14.2536*		1.5438	,000
		Currently	-6.0723*		1.2015	,000

4. There are differences in the irrational behavior of Economics Teachers based on appreciation of economic conditions.

The results of the first hypothesis test in this research can be presented in the following analysis results table:

Table 7. ANOVA

Irrational Behavior						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups		6153.297	2	3076.649	38,054	,000
Within Groups		21101.578	261	80,849		
Total		27254.875	263			
	(i) Economic Appreciation	(j) Economic Appreciation	Mean Difference (Ij)		Std. Error	Sig.
Tuk ey HS D	Tall	Currently	5.5370*		1.4261	,000
		Low	12.0235*		1.3956	,000
	Currently	Tall	-5.5370*		1.4261	,000
		Low	6.4866*		1.2928	,000
	Low	Tall	-12.0235*		1.3956	,000
		Currently	-6.4866*		1.2928	,000
Sch effe	Tall	Currently	5.5370*		1.4261	,001
		Low	12.0235*		1.3956	,000
	Currently	Tall	-5.5370*		1.4261	,001
		Low	6.4866*		1.2928	,000
	Low	Tall	-12.0235*		1.3956	,000
		Currently	-6.4866*		1.2928	,000

5. There are differences in the irrational behavior of Economics Teachers based on their commitment to emulate.

The results of the first hypothesis test in this research can be presented in the following analysis results table:

Table 8. ANOVA

ANOVA						
Irrational Behavior						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
	Between Groups	6792.458	2	3396.229	43,319	,000
	Within Groups	20462.417	261	78,400		
	Total	27254.875	263			
	(I) Commitment to Emulate	(J) Commitment to Emulate	Mean Difference (I-J)		Std. Error	Sig.
Tukey HS D	Tall	Currently	7.3161*		1.4669	,000
		Low	13.8008*		1.5006	,000
	Currently	Tall	-7.3161*		1.4669	,000
		Low	6.4847*		1.2247	,000
	Low	Tall	-13.8008*		1.5006	,000
		Currently	-6.4847*		1.2247	,000
Scheffe	Tall	Currently	7.3161*		1.4669	,000
		Low	13.8008*		1.5006	,000
	Currently	Tall	-7.3161*		1.4669	,000
		Low	6.4847*		1.2247	,000
	Low	Tall	-13.8008*		1.5006	,000
		Currently	-6.4847*		1.2247	,000

Discussion

From the results of descriptive data analysis, it is proven that the irrational behavior of economics teachers varies and is distributed normally. Variations in the data also prove that there are economics teachers who have very low levels of irrational behavior and also very high levels of irrational behavior. In this research, this variation is seen from five factors which are used as differentiating factors. The five factors in question include: level of professional capability, appreciation of educational conditions, level of subjective well-being, appreciation of economic conditions and commitment to emulate. Of these five factors, professional capability, subjective well-being and commitment to emulate are internal factors, while appreciation of educational conditions and appreciation of economic conditions are external factors.

It has been proven that economics teachers' irrational behavior varies in intensity based on their level of professional capability. This means that economics teachers with high professional capabilities have a high intensity of economic irrational behavior and vice versa. This can be understood considering that economics teachers with a high level of professional capability tend to earn high incomes through the activity and high frequency with which they carry out their profession as teachers. On the other hand, it cannot be denied that teachers with high professional capabilities certainly have the potential to increase expenditure to finance their profession.

The same results in testing the second hypothesis, namely, there are differences in the irrational behavior of economics teachers based on appreciation of educational conditions. In this case, the higher the level of appreciation for educational conditions, the higher the intensity of irrational behavior of economics teachers. As is generally known, the condition of education in this country can be said to be still less than ideal as expected by the founding fathers of the nation, as well as most educational circles.

The high appreciation of the existing educational conditions among economics teachers actually proves that they do not understand and critically observe the current educational conditions in this country. It is no wonder that such people also have a high intensity of irrational behavior. For the third hypothesis, there are differences in the irrational behavior of economics teachers based on their subjective well-being. This means that the higher the level of subjective well-being of an economics teacher, the higher the intensity of his irrational behavior.

This is understandable considering that teachers with a high level of subjective well-being usually have a high level of socio-economic life. With a high level of socio-economic life, of course economic behavior tends to be irrational, because they are often trapped in high consumption patterns, less interested in investing, because of the urge to enjoy the economic life they have achieved. Thus, it can be understood that subjective welfare factors can be a differentiating factor in the intensity of economics teachers' irrational behavior.

The results of the fourth hypothesis test provide the same analysis results, namely that there are differences in the irrational behavior of economics teachers, differentiated according to appreciation of economic conditions. This differentiating factor is basically closely related to the economics teacher's knowledge, understanding and critical assessment of economic conditions. In contrast to educational conditions, economic conditions in this country are relatively better, with a growth rate above five percent, although in daily life it is evident that several basic commodities have experienced quite high price increases.

Economics teachers who have a high level of appreciation for economic conditions are proven to also have a high level of intensity of irrational behavior. This is thought to be because economics teachers view the future of economic life as optimistic, so they tend to be less careful and irrational in their economic behavior. The final hypothesis which aims to prove that there is a difference in the intensity of economic teachers' irrational behavior, differentiated based on their commitment to emulate, is also proven to be significant, meaning that the higher the commitment of economics teachers to emulate their students, the higher their intensity of irrational behavior.

This is actually somewhat contradictory, but it is reasonable to suspect that the majority of economics teachers who were subjects in this research do not understand the concept of irrational behavior, so they may not realize that in their daily lives their economic behavior is actually a reflection of irrational behavior..

Conclusion

1. There are differences in the irrational behavior of Economics Teachers based on professional capabilities.
2. There are differences in the irrational behavior of Economics Teachers based on appreciation of educational conditions.
3. There are differences in the irrational behavior of Economics Teachers based on level of subjective well-being.
4. There are differences in the irrational behavior of Economics Teachers based on appreciation of economic conditions.

5. There are differences in the irrational behavior of Economics Teachers based on commitment to emulate.

The higher the level the level of professional capability, appreciation of educational conditions, level of subjective well-being, appreciation of economic conditions and commitment to emulate, the higher the intensity of irrational behavior of economics teachers and vice versa

Acknowledgment

Thank you to the supervisors who have provided support in carrying out this research and all parties who have contributed to this research, hopefully it will be of benefit.

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